

ISic0543

I.Sicily inscription 0543

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

urn

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Parthenicum

Place of origin (modern)

Partinico

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Partinico (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Aeliae Aug[e]

2. coniugi

3. sancitissimae

4. Publius Aelius Augusti libertus

5. [N]igr[ia]nus

Apparatus

Text of CIL with supplement in line 5 of Manganaro

Auria 1697: [..]IGR[.]NVS[.]; Gualtherus 1624: ΛΙGRANIVS

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491766

EDCS 22000850

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7264 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 50

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